

D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies

Date: April 30, 2026

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

Document Identification			
Status	Final	Due Date	30/04/2026
Version	1.0	Submission Date	30/04/2026

Related WP	WP4	Document Reference	D4.2
Related Deliverable(s)		Dissemination Level (*)	PU
Lead Participant	ATOS	Lead Author	Jesús Gorroñoigoitia (ATOS)
Contributors	SZE, UNISTRA, PSNC, MTG, FAU, USTUTT, ATOS	Reviewers	Michal Kulczewski (PSNC)
			László Környei (SZE)

Keywords:

data management, data ingestion, data transfer, coupling technologies, FAIR data, HPC data transfer, simulation coupling, digital twin, scientific data sharing, data interoperability

Disclaimer for Deliverables with dissemination level PUBLIC

This document is issued within the frame and for the purpose of the HiDALGO2 project. Funded by the European Union. This work has received funding from the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) and Poland, Germany, Spain, Hungary, France, Greece under grant agreement number: 101093457. This publication expresses the opinions of the authors and not necessarily those of the EuroHPC JU and Associated Countries which are not responsible for any use of the information contained in this publication. **This deliverable is subject to final acceptance by the European Commission.**

This document and its content are the property of the HiDALGO2 Consortium. The content of all or parts of this document can be used and distributed provided that the HiDALGO2 project and the document are properly referenced.

Each HiDALGO2 Partner may use this document in conformity with the HiDALGO2 Consortium Grant Agreement provisions.

(*) Dissemination levels: **PU**: Public, fully open, e.g. web; **SEN**: Sensitive, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement; **EU-C**: **European Union Classified**, the unauthorised disclosure of this information could harm the essential interests of the Consortium.

Document Information

List of Contributors	
Name	Partner
Jesus Gorroñoigoitia Cruz	ATOS
Ángela Rivera	MTG
Luis Torres	MTG
Piotr Dzierzak	PSNC
Michal Kulczewski	PSNC
Krzysztof Kotecki	PSNC
Christophe Prud'homme	UNISTRA
Gwendolé Chappron	UNISTRA
Vincent Chabannes	UNISTRA
Zoltán Horváth	SZE
László Környei	SZE
Harald Koestler	FAU
Ravi Kiran	FAU

Document History			
Version	Date	Change editors	Changes
0.1	26/01/2026	Jesús Gorroñoigoitia (ATOS)	Table of Contents
0.2	09/02/2026	Marcin Lawenda (PSNC), Rahil Doshi (FAU)	ToC, timeline and responsibilities approved
0.3	24/03/2026	Christophe Prud'homme (UNISTRA), Piotr Dzierzak (PSNC)	Section 2

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	3 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

		Ángela Rivera(MTG), Jesús Gorroñoigoitia(ATOS)	
0.4	8/04/2026	Jesús Gorroñoigoitia(ATOS), Christophe Prud'homme, Gwenolé Chappron (UNISTRA), Luis Torres (MTG), Michal Kulczewski, Krzysztof Kotecki (PSNC), Ravi Kiran (FAU)	Sections 1 and 3
0.5	9/04/2026	Christophe Prud'homme, Vincent Chabannes (UNISTRA), László Környei (SZE), Piotr Dzierzak (PSNC)	Sections 2 and 3
0.6	13/04/2026	Jesús Gorroñoigoitia(ATOS)	Version ready for internal review
0.9	27/04/2026	Michał Kulczwski (PSNC), László Környei (SZE), Jesús Gorroñoigoitia(ATOS)	Version ready for quality check
0.95	29/04/2026	Shubham Kavane	Quality assurance check
1.0	30/04/2026	Marcin Lawenda	Final check and improvements

Quality Control		
Role	Who (Partner short name)	Approval Date
Deliverable Leader	Jesús Gorroñoigoitia (ATOS)	29/04/2026
Quality Manager	Shubham Kavane (FAU)	29/04/2026
Project Coordinator	Marcin Lawenda (PSNC)	30/04/2026

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	4 of 72	
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status:	Final

Table of Contents

Document Information	3
Table of Contents	5
List of Tables	6
List of Figures	6
List of Acronyms	7
Executive Summary	10
1 Introduction	11
1.1 Purpose of the document	11
1.2 Relation to other project work	12
1.3 Structure of the document	12
2 Data Management	14
2.1 Requirements	14
2.2 Functional Specification	14
2.2.1 Data Storage	14
2.2.2 Data Transfer	15
2.2.3 Data Interoperability	17
2.3 DMS Architecture	17
2.4 DMS Implementation and Deployment	20
2.4.1 CKAN Storage	20
2.4.2 HDFS Storage	21
2.4.3 Data Transfer	24
2.5 DMS Evaluation	35
3 Coupling Technologies	39
3.1 UAP and UBM coupling	39
3.2 WFs and UAP coupling	43
3.3 WFs and MTW coupling	47
3.4 RES and UBM coupling	52
3.5 UBM and WRF coupling	55

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	5 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

3.6 RES and WRF coupling58

4 Conclusions60

References61

Annex I: CKAN-Zenodo exporter – configuration example65

Annex II: CKAN2HPC-Client – configuration example.....66

Annex III: Performance benchmarking of Data Transfer Tool (Charts).....67

List of Tables

Table 1. VMs for HDFS deployment 23

Table 2. HDFS/YARN Web Services 23

Table 3. Data Transfer Benchmarks 38

Table 4. Emission factors 44

Table 5. Empirical parameters (I) 50

Table 6. Empirical parameters (II) 50

Table 7. Verified result for a moderate-regime case 51

List of Figures

Figure 1. DMS Architecture 18

Figure 2. Deployment schema for HiDALGO2 HDFS and YARN Computing 22

Figure 3. CKAN-Zenodo exporter schema 25

Figure 4. NIFI deployment 27

Figure 5. architecture of kub-dataset 34

Figure 6. Data upload using CKAN2HPC-Client 35

Figure 7. Data download using CKAN2HPC-Client 36

Figure 8. UAP-UBM coupling workflow 42

Figure 9. Data flow for the UAP-WFs coupling 46

Figure 10. Work-flow orchestration for the WF-MTW coupling 48

Figure 11. Coupling site locations 54

Figure 12. Data workflow 54

Figure 13. Work-flow orchestration for the UBM-WRF coupling 57

Figure 14 CKAN2HPC Data Transfer throughput (Mb/s) vs # concurrent transfer tasks after optimization 1 67

Figure 15 Data Transfer throughput (Mb/s) vs # concurrent transfer tasks after optimization 1 68

Figure 16 Data Transfer throughput (Mb/s) vs # concurrent transfer tasks after optimization 1 69

Figure 17 CKAN2HPC Data Transfer throughput (Mb/s) vs # concurrent transfer tasks after optimizations 2 and 3 70

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	6 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 18 CKAN2HDFS Data Transfer throughput (Mb/s) vs # concurrent transfer tasks after optimizations 2 and 3 _____ 71

Figure 19 HPC2HDFS Data Transfer throughput (Mb/s) vs # concurrent transfer tasks after optimizations 2 and 3 _____ 72

List of Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
2FA	Two Factor Authentication
ACID	Atomicity, Consistency, Isolation, Durability
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment
CKAN	Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network
CLI	Command Line Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRUD	Create Read Update Delete
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DMS	Data Management System
DWD	Deutscher Wetterdienst
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FBFM40	Scott and Burgan Fire Behavior Fuel Models
GB	Gigabyte
GPS	Global Positioning System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HDFS	Hadoop File System
HPC	High Performance Computing
HPDA	High Performance Data Analytics

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	7 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

HTTP(S)	(Secured) Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IAM	Identity Access Management
IB	Byram envisioned fireline intensity
IDM	Identity Management
JSON	Java Script Object Notation
KUB	Ktirio Urban Building
LTS	Long Term Support
MPI	Message Passing Interface
MTG	MeteoGrid
MTW	Material Transport in Water
M<X>	Month <x>
NAR	Nix Archive Format
OIDC	OpenID Connect
OM	Open Meteo
OSM	Open Street Maps
OSS	Open-Source Software
PKCE	Proof Key for Code Exchange
PSD	Particle Size Distribution
RAM	Random Access Memory
RES	Renewal Energy Sources
REST	Representational State Transfer
(S)FTP	(Secure) File Transfer Protocol
SoTA	State of the Art
SQL	Structured Query Language
SSH	Secure Shell
SSO	Single Sign On
TB	Terabyte
UAP	Urban Air Project
UBM	Urban Building Model
UML	Unified Modelling Language
UQ	Uncertainty Quantification
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VM	Virtual Machine
VPN	Virtual Private Network
WCS	Web Coverage Service

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	8 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

WF	Wildfire
WFO	Workflow Orchestrator
WP<X>	Work-package <X>
WRF	Weather Research and Forecasting
WSGI	Web Server Gateway Interface
XML	Extensible Markup Language
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language
YARN	Yet Another Resource Negotiator

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	9 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Executive Summary

This deliverable is the follow up of D4.1 Data Management and Coupling Technologies M11 [1]. It reports on the progress attained in the development of the HiDALGO2 Data Management System [DMS] and the coupling technologies required by the realization of the WP5 coupling scenarios [2] since the last D4.1 report. The HiDALGO2 DMS provides the framework that supports the provisioning of data required for the deployment and execution of different variants of pilots’ scenarios simulations [3], including massive ensemble [4] simulations for Uncertainty Quantification [5] and benchmarking [6], as well as for the exploitation of simulation results. The coupling technologies incorporates results from the HiDALGO2 toolset, including the Workflow Orchestrators (WFOs) [7], the DMS, and Visualization Technologies [8], as well as other third-party frameworks and in-house coupling and codebase adaptation developments, to enable the realization of pilots’ coupling scenarios.

Since D4.1, significant progress has been attained in the DMS, addressing most of the requirements elicited from pilots’ stakeholders, and other HiDALGO2 technical work packages, thereby extending its functional scope. To achieve this functionality, the DMS technical architecture has been revisited, resulting in a new functional specification, and the DMS storage, based on CKAN and Hadoop HDFS/YARN has been updated accordingly. The data transfer functionality has been largely improved, in terms of functionality and performance, whose evaluation is also reported, with specialized tooling for CKAN transfer, for multi-backend transfer, powered by Apache NIFI and the KUB platforms, including transfer support from Cloud, CKAN, HDFS and HPC providers and consumers.

Quite a significant progress has also been achieved on the technical development of the coupling scenarios, with the adoption and development of diverse coupling technologies for the realization of a higher number of coupling scenarios than those depicted in D4.1. HiDALGO2 technologies, such as the WFOs for automatic management of coupling pipelines, DMS for data sharing and transfer, in-house developed lightweight MPI- interoperability layers, tight coupling frameworks, shared data schema, pilots’ codebases adaptations and other strategies for coupling technologies have been adopted, or implemented since D4.1. HiDALGO2 has explored coupling scenarios with different topologies, including one vs. two-way coupling, and light-weight vs. tight-weight coupling.

The HiDALGO2 DMS constitutes the foundational technology for data provisioning, exploitation and sharing of HPC exa-scale simulations. This technology, together with the HiDALGO2 WFOs and others coupling dedicated frameworks, largely simplify the combination of CFD-based simulations on holistic coupling scenarios, as exemplified by the HiDALGO2 pilots.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	10 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document is the follow up of the document D4.1 Data Management and Coupling Technologies, released by M11 [1]. That document accounted for the functional specification, based on elicited requirements from pilot’s stakeholders, the SoTA for baseline technologies, and the technical architecture design and initial implementation of the HiDALGO2 Data Management System (DMS). It is also addressed the initial identification and description of pilot’s coupling scenarios and the SoTA on coupling technologies that the development of those scenarios leverages.

The HiDALGO2 DMS enables data intensive driven analytics conducted by T4.2 HPDA, and the execution of pilot simulations and coupling scenarios, within the orchestrations managed by T2.4 Workflow Orchestration (WFO) engines, as well as the visualization of simulation results with T4.4 visualization tools, the post-execution management of T3.3 ensemble simulations and T4.6 uncertainty quantification resulting datasets.

The coupling technologies procure the tooling required to enact the coupling of the pilot simulations within a holistic scenario, tools borrowed from other HiDALGO2 WPs, including the T4.1 DMS or the T2.4 WFOs, as well as from the adoption of third-party frameworks or the implementation of required pilot’s codebase changes to realize the coupling.

Since then, both the HiDALGO2 DMS and the adopted/implemented coupling technologies have shown a significant progress, which is reported in this document.

In particular, the DMS has improved the data storage support, integrating complementary storage solutions, based on i) CKAN [9] for scientific dataset sharing, and ii) Apache Hadoop HDFS, for highly scalable and data-intensive computing support for HPDA, which addresses the FAIR principles that motivated the HiDALGO2 DMS design. Complementing the data storage, DMS incorporates data transfer solutions, including i) the CKAN Zenodo exporter, ii) CKAN2HPC transfer tool, iii) the Apache NIFI [10] powered data transfer lib and CLI for high-performance data exchange between Cloud providers, CKAN and HDFS storage and HPC providers/consumers, and iv) the KUB multi-backed data management, powering multi-storage data transfer among multiple data storage for CI/CD pipelines.

On the regard the coupling technologies, additional coupling scenarios have been identified and specified since D4.1. For all these scenarios, different HiDALGO2 technologies, mostly the WP4 DMS and the WP2 WFOs and CI/CD pipelines have been adopted. The pilot’s codebases have been modified and/or extended to exchange new versions of their consumed/produced datasets with improved schema

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	11 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

and/or agreed exchange formats for data exchange, as well as to support inter-pilot integration with simulation orchestrations and/or tightly coupled execution synchronization.

In the following subsections, this document accounts for this progress on both main topics: the HiDALGO2 DMS and the Coupling Technologies.

1.2 Relation to other project work

The progress reported in this document is quite related to other project work. The T4.1 HiDALGO2 DMS provide horizontal technology adopted by other tasks, and all pilot’s verticals. In particular, T2.4 WFO engines integrated the DMS data storage and data transfer frameworks for the provisioning of input datasets required by pilot simulations, as well as for the procurement of simulation resulting datasets. Both input/output simulations datasets are amenable to pre/post-simulation HPDA(T4.2) and visualization (T4.4). On this regard, both T3.3 Ensembles and T4.6 Uncertainty Quantification generate huge amount of simulation results that are stored in the DMS storage.

The reported coupling technologies are closely related to WP5 tasks, where pilots’ applications, scenarios and couplings are identified and specified. T4.5 coupling technologies work on the procurement of the technical developments that enable pilots’ applications to interoperate in these coupling scenarios.

1.3 Structure of the document

The structure of this document is organized as follows.

Section 2 reports the progress in the specification, technical design, development and evaluation of the HiDALGO2 DMS.

Section 2.1 reports on the changes in DMS requirements since D4.1.

Section 2.2 reports the updated functional specification of the DMS platform, in terms of data storage (Section 2.2.1), Data Transfer (Section 2.2.2) and Data Interoperability (Section 2.2.3).

Section 2.3 reports on the updated technical architecture design of the DMS platform.

Section 2.4 reports on the updated implementation of the DMS platform, concretely Section 2.4.1 on the CKAN storage deployment, Section 2.4.2 on the Apache Hadoop HDFS/YARN deployment, and Section 2.4.3 on the implementation of the Data Transfer multi-faceted solution.

Section 2.5 reports on the evaluation of the performance of the DMS Data Transfer solution.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	12 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Section 3 reports on the progress of the development of the technologies involved in the realization of the pilots' coupling scenarios, with subsections for each coupling.

Section 0 concludes the document with a summary of main achievements and planned future work.

Annexes in sections I, II, and III provides auxiliary information related to i) the CKAN-Zenodo exporter configuration, ii) the CKAN2HPC client configuration and iii) the charts of the performance benchmarking of the DMS Data Transfer tooling, respectively.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	13 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

2 Data Management

This section reports on updates in the requirements, the functional and technical specification, the implementation evolution, and the performance evaluation of the HiDALGO2 data management system (DMS).

2.1 Requirements

Requirements for HiDALGO2 DMS has been expressed by pilot’s and other technical stakeholders in different periods of the project past time, and reported in D4.1 [1], and the series of deliverables on project requirements: D2.1 [11], D2.2 [12] and D2.3 [13]. Complementing those requirements, HPDA stakeholders have expressed the need to conduct analytics for huge volumes of data in a distributed, scalable computing infrastructure closely connected to the same infrastructure that host the same HiDALGO2 DMS storage.

2.2 Functional Specification

This section updates the description of features implemented by the DMS, split into those related to data storage, data transfer and interoperability with other HiDALGO2 services.

2.2.1 Data Storage

The HiDALGO2 DMS storage is hosted on the Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC) CEPH [14] filesystem, which provides a scalable and highly reliable distributed storage solution. Currently, the storage capacity amounts to 20 TB and is distributed across the infrastructure to ensure redundancy and performance. This storage is mounted directly on the data nodes, allowing efficient access to data for processing tasks and enabling high-throughput operations within the system.

The functionality of the DMS storage has evolved since its specification in D4.1. Compared to the previous implementation, one feature has not been fully supported, some have been managed in slightly different manner as conceived in D4.1 and new ones have been incorporated.

Dataset versioning and tracking has not been fully supported by all DMS components, as not required by most of pilot’s stakeholders and external users, but can be enabled in CKAN storage by plug in one of the available extensions, and it is supported by the KUB Multi-Backend DM (see section 2.4.3.5).

Dataset querying is now supported through the HDFS/YARN/Spark platform (see section 2.3) for HPDA applications requiring querying (semi) structured data.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	14 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Compared to D4.1, SQL-like querying is not supported as there is no demand from pilots.

REST APIs for data CRUD operations and querying/search is supported by CKAN, HDFS and the KUB Multi-Backend DM. Web interfaces and APIs are available for these operations in the DMS storage engines. They also provide CLI interfaces supporting these operations.

Metadata/Catalogue for dataset management is supported by CKAN. This storage constitutes the HiDALGO2 reference data storage implementation for data sharing and dissemination.

All the services included in the HiDALGO2 DMS are secured for both IAM and AAI with Keycloak [15] and Kerberos [16] (see section 2.3). The access to CKAN (REST API, Web) and data transfer NIFI (REST API, Web) is granted by account or access key, controlled by Keycloak. The access to HDFS data storage and other Hadoop [17] ecosystem services (see section 2.3) is granted by Kerberos. Data privacy and data access rights can be established in both CKAN and HDFS storage by user, groups (organizations in case of CKAN) and datasets (folders in case of HDFS). The KUB Multi-Backend DM also relies on Keycloak/OIDC IAM providers.

Redundant data storage is supported by HDFS [18], to avoid data lost. However, to maximize the available data storage, HDFS has been configured with no replication, but this configuration can be changed in production on demand.

See sections 2.4.1, 2.4.2 and 2.4.3 for more details of services and implementation.

2.2.2 Data Transfer

Similarly, the functionality of the HiDALGO2 Data Transfer implementation has significantly evolved since its specification in D4.1. Compared to the previous implementation, some features have been extended and new ones incorporated. Different mechanisms for data transfer have been developed, namely:

- CKAN-powered data transfer,
- NIFI-powered data transfer.

The CKAN-powered data transfer (bidirectional transfer to and from CKAN DMS storage) is handled through two main mechanisms: the CKAN API and the SFTP protocol.

The CKAN API enables programmatic interaction with the data repository, allowing users and services to upload, download, and manage datasets in an automated and structured way. This is particularly useful for integrating external applications, scheduling data ingestion pipelines, and maintaining metadata consistency across the platform.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	15 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

In addition, direct file transfers are supported via SFTP, which provides a secure and reliable method for moving large datasets. Using encrypted connections over SSH, SFTP ensures data integrity and confidentiality during transfer. This method is especially suitable for bulk data uploads and downloads, as well as for users who prefer command-line or script-based data management workflows.

The NIFI-powered DMS Data Transfer provides high performance, parallel, data transfer among HiDALGO2 data providers (i.e., data sources) and consumers (i.e., data targets) . As data providers, this tool supports: i) Cloud providers, such as ECWMF and MeteoFrance Arpege, ii) HiDALGO2 DMS storage (CKAN, HDFS), iii) SSH-accessible HPC centres, and iv) local storage in any utility computer (e.g. Laptops, workstations, servers). As data consumers, this tool supports: i) HiDALGO2 DMS storage (CKAN, HDFS), and ii) SSH-accessible HPC centres.

That is, the Data Transfer tool support the one-directional transfer of data:

- From local storage (e.g., computer file system) to CKAN or HDFS,
- From Cloud providers to CKAN, HDFS and HPC,

And the bidirectional transfer of data between:

- CKAN and HDFS,
- CKAN and HPC,
- HDFS and HPC.

Data Transfer tool permits data transfer from/to any of the EuroHPC JU centres [19]. It supports IAM with Keycloak and Kerberos. Keycloak is required to get granted access to the Data Transfer NIFI backend and the CKAN storage, and Kerberos to get granted access to the HDFS storage. To get access to the EuroHPC JU centres, the Data Transfer tool supports: i) SSH credentials, keys and certificates, ii) 2FA, and iii) VPN access¹.

Data Transfer tool provides a Python library, intended for integrating its functionality by other HiDALGO2 and third-party services. This library is also used by the Data Transfer CLI, which offers a command line functionality for end-users.

Data Transfer tools incorporates a number of optimizations, powered by NIFI, including concurrent transfer tasks, and streamline pipeline execution. It has also incorporated fault-tolerance management to avoid data lost during transfer to HPC.

Flexible selection of data sets/files/folders to transfer is supported with wildcards as well as the transfer of nested directories.

Data transfer accounting is also supported, informing the total bytes transferred, total transfer time and rate.

¹ VPN access is supported by white-listing the NIFI server in the EuroHPC JU centre that requires it.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	16 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

The data transfer functionality of the KUB Multi-Backend DM is reported in section 2.4.3.5.

See section 2.4.3 for more details of services and implementation.

2.2.3 Data Interoperability

The HiDALGO2 DMS offers APIs and other mechanisms to interoperate with other HiDALGO2 services.

Data transfer functionality is offered as Python API to be integrated by the HiDALGO2 WFOs, namely QCG and MathSO [7]. These WFOs can use this library for the provisioning of input dataset required by HPC job execution upon submission. These datasets can be transferred from CKAN, HDFS or Cloud providers to the target HPC centre by using the Data Transfer library. Similarly, the results of HPC job execution can be transferred back to the HiDALGO2 CKAN or HDFS storage upon job termination, using the Data Transfer library, for further HPDA, visualization or scientific dissemination.

Moreover, the HiDALGO2 DMS provides a data-intensive computation framework, suited for HPDA computations. This framework is connected to the HiDALGO2 development platform, powered by the Jupyter Hub [20], where developers can run HPDA scripts in notebooks. These computations are sent to a Spark [21] back-end running on top of Hadoop YARN [22] distributed computing (see section 2.3), closely connected to the HDFS distributed storage. This way, computations are run at the same computing platform that hosts the data, showing a significant performance boosting.

2.3 DMS Architecture

The architecture design of the HiDALGO2 DMS has evolved since the initial proposal reported in D4.1, mostly motivated by two main reasons: i) to accommodate the design to the actual needs expressed by pilot’s stakeholders and other HiDALGO2 technical work-packages or tasks during this reporting period, and ii) to manage the technical suitability of selected baseline technologies. In the following, we discuss the current DMS architecture, shown in Figure 1CKAN Storage , focusing on the main changes since the last version and the reasons that motivated them.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	17 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 1 DMS Architecture

Components filled in green have been development from scratch. The other components are instances of OSS packages selected in the SoTA baseline.

Core components of the DMS are: i) the Data Storage components, ii) the Data Transfer components, and, iii) the Data Computing components. Compared to the D4.1 architecture design, the Hadoop Data Storage has been simplified around the Hadoop HDFS, removing unnecessary Hadoop services. Other components included in the D4.1 architecture has been removed or replaced by alternative choices.

The Hadoop ecosystem deployment and management with Ambari [23] has been abandoned, as the Ambari catalogues for Hadoop are no longer available in the public domain. The entire Hadoop ecosystem is installed, configured and managed manually. The deployment and configuration automation using SoTA solutions such as Ansible

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	18 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

or container-based solutions such as Docker [24], Kubernetes [25] or Helm [26] are left for future work.

The data querying functionality for HPDA and AI, supported by Hive [27] in the D4.1 architecture, is supported, in the new D4.2 architecture, by the Data Computing platform described in following sections.

Metadata and catalogue management, offered by Atlas [28] in D4.1 architecture, is managed by CKAN in D4.2, as pilot’s users are mostly adopting CKAN for dataset sharing and advertising, but not HDFS.

DataLake features such as ACID transactions and data versioning, offered by Hudi [29], are not required by pilots’ stakeholders, thereby this component has not been included in D4.2 architecture.

Nonetheless, in future releases of the DMS architecture, any of the above discarded Hadoop components could be recovered back, if their functionality is required by pilot’s stakeholders or other external users.

An addition to D4.1 architecture is the inclusion of the Data Computing platform, required by HPDA to run data-intensive analytics. The proposed solution consists of a distributed computing infrastructure, based on the Apache Hadoop YARN, which is tightly integrated with the distributed Hadoop HDFS. Within this infrastructure, the Spark analytics engine is installed, to offer large-scale data analytics processing. To serve the YARN-Spark engine as a REST interface, a Livy [30] server is included as middleware. This analytics infrastructure is accessed by engineers within the HiDALGO2 online development platform, based on the Jupyter Hub. The engineer’s Jupyter notebook uses the Sparkmagic [31] kernel (installed in the Jupyter Hub) to submit HPDA tasks to the YARN-Spark computing platform, through the Livy middleware.

The components of the Hadoop ecosystem, including the HDFS and YARN platforms, the HUE [32] frontend for HDFS and the Livy middleware are secured by Kerberos, which provides IAM and AAI support.

CKAN functionality has been extended to promote data sharing and scientific dissemination with the inclusion of the exporter to Zenodo [33], enabling data providers to migrate their CKAN dataset to Zenodo (see section 2.4.3.1).

Some data transfer components are available, namely: i) the NIFI-powered data transfer, ii) the CKAN2HPC CLI, and the iii) KUB Multi-backend CLI. The NIFI-powered data transfer framework consists of a Data Transfer Library, that implements the functionality for data transfer across several data providers and consumers, including external Cloud data providers, external HPC data providers/consumers and the HiDALGO2 Data Storage (HDFS, CKAN). This library is used by i) HiDALGO2 WFOs, such as QCG and MathSO for the provisioning of job input data before submission and

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	19 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

the storage of job results, and ii) the Data Transfer CLI, which offers data transfer operations to end-users. The Data Transfer Library interfaces the NIFI engine to run their pipelines that perform highly parallel and efficient data transfer across HiDALGO2 and external data providers/consumers. The CKAN2HPC CLI supports the bidirectional transfer of datasets between CKAN and HPC, with higher throughput compared to the performance offered by the CKAN REST API. The KUB Multi-backend CLI offers a common interface for data transfer among CKAN, HDFS and S3-compatible object storages.

Some components of the HiDALGO2 DMA use Keycloak as IAM/AAI backend, inline to the other HiDALGO2 services. This backed is seamlessly integrated with the HiDALGO2 services, including the following DMS ones: CKAN, NIFI and Data Transfer. Hadoop ecosystem tools use the Kerberos back-end. The integration of Keycloak and Kerberos is left as future work. Despite this double-authentication is not optimal, it shows little impact of final users, as Kerberos authentication last for 12 hours before it needs to be renewed.

2.4 DMS Implementation and Deployment

This section reports the updated details of the implementation and deployment of the different components of the HiDALGO2 DMS, referring to D4.1 for comparing progress.

2.4.1 CKAN Storage

The CKAN is installed in the PSNC OpenStack infrastructure. The virtual machine with 8vCPU and 16GB RAM is running on Ubuntu Server 22.04 LTS Linux. The CKAN web interface is accessible via HTTPS protocol. Additional storage for database and data is located on the CEPH infrastructure. The volume for the storage is 2 TB with opportunity to extend the size.

The server with CKAN is also configured to upload data using SFTP protocol. The files are stored in the user’s home directories and accessible via HTTPS on dedicated virtual host or SFTP. Only SSH keys are used to log in to SFTP.

CKAN is integrated with HiDALGO2 IDM, which is regularly updated. The CKAN services are monitored using HiDALGO2’s Zabbix [34] system.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	20 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

2.4.2 HDFS Storage

The HiDALGO2 DMS HDFS storage and distributed YARN Computing platform have been deployed into the PSNC Cloud virtual platform, in VMs (see Table 1) according to the deployment schema depicted in Figure 2 as an UML deployment diagram.

Seven PSNC Cloud VM nodes are used for HDFS/YARN deployment: i) one for hosting the Cloudera HUE frontend, ii) one acting as the Kerberos server, the HDFS namenode and the YARN resource manager, iii) another one acting as the HDFS secondary namenode, and iv) 4 nodes acting as HDFS datanodes and YARN node managers. Additional datanodes/nodemangers can be added on demand.

The Kerberos authentication service (version 1.19.2) has been deployed in the namenode, acting as the AAI component. The artifact *kdc.conf* provides the server-side configuration of the Kerberos Key Distribution Center (KDC) for the HIDALGO2.COM realm, while the artifact *krb5.conf* provides the client-side interface to the KDC.

The HUE GUI (version 4.11.0) is deployed in a dedicated node from Docker images using docker-compose. Its configuration file *hue.ini* has been modified to: i) configure Kerberos security and connection to HDFS, YARN, Spark and Livy services, ii) disable other not-required Hadoop services.

The Hadoop HDFS and YARN services (version 3.3.6) are deployed in different nodes, with the same shared configuration. The artifact *core-site.xml* sets the configuration of the HDFS endpoint and enables Kerberos configuration for its main services. The artifact *hdfs-site.xml* configures the HDFS services, including the namenode, secondary namenode and datanodes, and their Kerberos principals and keytab configuration.

Different *keytab* files, referenced in aforementioned artifacts, have been created for the different HDFS services and Web portals, containing the Kerberos keys associated to their principals.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	21 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 2 Deployment schema for HiDALGO2 HDFS and YARN Computing

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	22 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

The list of datanodes available for HDFS and YARN have been declared in the *workers* artifact. The YARN resource manager and node manager services are configured with the *yarn-site.xml* artifact. It sets the resource manager host, the resources for the node managers and the scheduler, some Spark configuration and the Kerberos configuration.

Table 1 VMs for HDFS deployment

VM	CPU	RAM	DISK	FQDN	Role
hue	8	16 Gb	500 Gb	prunus-106.man.poznan.pl	HDFS GUI
namenode	8	16 Gb	500 Gb	sophora-42.man.poznan.pl	HDFS namenode, YARN resource manager
secondary_namenode	8	8 Gb	500 Gb	sophora-103.man.poznan.pl	HDFS secondary namenode
datanode1	16	32 Gb	10 Tb	prunus-209.man.poznan.pl	HDFS datanode, YARN node manager
datanode2	16	32 Gb	10 Tb	sophora-109.man.poznan.pl	HDFS datanode, YARN node manager
datanode3	16	32 Gb	10 Tb	prunus-210.man.poznan.pl	HDFS datanode, YARN node manager
datanode4	16	32 Gb	10 Tb	onoclea-167.man.poznan.pl	HDFS datanode, YARN node manager

The *mapred-site.xml* artifact sets the resources and Kerberos configuration for the YARN map-reduce component. All these HDFS configuration artifacts have been distributed across the HDFS nodes. The current HDFS storage capacity is 40 Tb. HDFS file replication has been set to 1 to maximize the storage.

Several Kerberos-secured Web portals are available for users (see Table 2):

Table 2 HDFS/YARN Web Services

HDFS Portal	URL	Role
HDFS Portal	http://sophora-42.man.poznan.pl:9870	HDFS Administration, Simple Data Browser
YARN Portal	http://sophora-42.man.poznan.pl:8088/cluster	YARN Administration, Application browser
Livy Portal	http://sophora-42.man.poznan.pl:8998/ui	Livy Session Administration
HUE Portal	http://prunus-106.man.poznan.pl/hue	Advance Data Browser

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	23 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

The Spark framework (version 3.5.3) has been deployed across all the HDFS nodes. Its *spark-defaults.conf* artifact sets the Kerberos configuration, connection to YARN and executor resources.

The Livy server acts as middleware between Web clients and Spark/YARN computing infrastructure. It is deployed in the HDFS namenode. Its *live.conf* artifact configures its endpoint, the connection to YARN and the Kerberos security.

2.4.3 Data Transfer

This section reports the updated details of the implementation and deployment of the different components of the HiDALGO2 DMS Data Transfer components, referring to D4.1 for comparing progress. The following subsections specialize the data-transfer implementations.

2.4.3.1 CKAN-based Data Transfer

PSNC developed the CKAN-Zenodo exporter to facilitate the transfer of research data from CKAN-based repositories to Zenodo [33].

The system enables exporting CKAN datasets and their associated metadata directly to Zenodo using the Zenodo API, allowing seamless publication and archiving of research data (see Figure 3). It is designed to support multiple users and configurable resource paths, which makes it suitable for multi-user environments and flexible deployment scenarios.

The application integrates Single Sign-On (SSO) authentication through Keycloak, providing centralized identity management and secure user access.

The frontend of the application is implemented using the Flask web framework [35], while the Waitress WSGI [36] server is used to serve the application in a production environment, ensuring stability and efficient request handling.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	24 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 3. CKAN-Zenodo exporter schema

An example of the CKAN-Zenodo exporter configuration file settings.ini is located at Annex I.

The backend is a Python application running as system service. To ensure reliable and scalable data transfers, the system utilizes a RabbitMQ-based [37] background queue, which handles dataset export tasks asynchronously and improves performance when processing multiple transfers. Additionally, the application is capable of transferring files stored in CKAN using two different methods: directly through the CKAN API [38] as well as through SFTP.

PSNC developed also the **CKAN2HPC-Client** – a Python client for integrating CKAN data portal with HPC environments.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	25 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

The tool enables efficient transfer of datasets between CKAN and HPC systems using SFTP or CKAN API while maintaining reproducibility, integrity, and scalable data handling. It is designed primarily for large scientific datasets that are stored outside CKAN (e.g. HPC storage) but managed through CKAN metadata.

Many scientific infrastructures use CKAN as a metadata catalogue while storing actual datasets in external storage such as:

- HPC clusters
- scientific storage systems

Uploading large files directly through CKAN is inefficient. This client solves that problem by:

- uploading files to HPC storage via SFTP
- registering dataset resources in CKAN
- enabling downloads via HTTP or SFTP

The tool acts as a bridge between CKAN metadata and HPC storage.

The application provides functionality for uploading both individual files and entire directories to the CKAN data repository. When a directory is selected for upload, it is automatically compressed into a ZIP archive, which simplifies the transfer process and ensures that the directory structure is preserved.

The system supports two different upload mechanisms. For large datasets, files can be transferred using SFTP, which provides a more efficient and reliable method for handling large volumes of data. Alternatively, files can also be uploaded directly through the CKAN API, allowing integration with standard CKAN data management workflows.

During the upload process, the application can automatically create a dataset in CKAN if the specified dataset does not yet exist. If the target organization cannot be identified, the system uses an automatic organization fallback mechanism, ensuring that the upload process can still be completed successfully.

To maintain data integrity and improve traceability, the application calculates a SHA256 checksum for each uploaded file. Additionally, files are assigned unique remote filenames, which prevents naming conflicts and ensures that multiple uploads do not overwrite existing resources.

The application also provides flexible options for retrieving data from CKAN repositories. Users can download entire datasets, which retrieves all resources

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	26 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

associated with a given dataset in a single operation. It is also possible to download individual resources, allowing users to retrieve only specific files when needed.

In addition to downloads through CKAN’s standard mechanisms, the application supports direct downloads from SFTP storage, enabling faster and more efficient access to large files stored outside the standard CKAN file storage system. This approach improves performance when working with large research datasets.

Example of CKAN2HPC-Client configuration file *settings.ini* is located at Annex II.

2.4.3.2 NIFI-based Data Transfer

The Data Transfer framework developed in the HiDALGO2 projects is powered by the Apache NIFI platform, which supports the development and highly efficient execution of data-processing pipelines. The NIFI platform, consisting on the NIFI engine and the NIFI registry, has been deployed in another VM node of the PSNC Cloud, according to the deployment schema depicted, as a UML deployment diagram, in the Figure 4.

Figure 4 NIFI deployment

The NIFI engine is configured by the artifacts *nifi.properties* and *bootstrap.conf*. The *nifi.properties* configures the OpenId Connect that NIFI uses to authenticate users with the HiDALGO2 Keycloak IDM. The *bootstrap.conf* configures the server resources that NIFI needs to maximize its throughput.

NIFI creates data transfer pipelines from templates stored in the NIFI Registry. It hosts versions of flow definitions (in XML) for all the process groups (e.g., the NIFI terminology for pipelines) required by the HiDALGO2 Data Transfer tool, namely:

- CKAN2HPC, HPC2CKAN pipelines,
- HPC2HDFS, HDFS2HPC pipelines,
- CKAN2HDFS, HDFS2CKAN pipelines,

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	27 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

- 2FA versions CKAN2HPC, HPC2CKAN, HDFS2HPC, HPC2HDFS pipelines,
- Local2CKAN, CKAN2Local pipelines,
- Cloud Providers (ARPEGE2, NOAA, ECMWF, MeteoFrance) to CKAN pipelines,
- Optimized versions, with parallel flows for some of above pipelines.

Throughout the DMS development lifecycle, NIFI server was updated from NIFI 1.X to NIFI 2.X. Current version is NIFI 2.8.

Two custom NIFI processors have been implemented to transfer data to/from CKAN: i) the CKANFileUploader, and the CKANFileDownloader. They are implemented in Java, and support parallel flowfile processing. They can create CKAN datasets on demand and read/write individual and multiple resources. They are only intended for data transfer and do not provide browsing or searching capabilities. The NAR files created for these CKAN processors are manually deployed in NIFI.

These custom CKAN processors are available at HiDALGO2 Gitlab [39].

It is planned as future work to set up a 2-node NIFI cluster to boost the data transfer performance, and benchmark the transfer throughput scaling with the number of nodes.

2.4.3.3 Data Transfer for CKAN, HDFS and HPC

The HiDALGO2 Data Transfer framework code base has significantly changed since D4.1. It is now split into 2 main components: i) a data transfer Python library, and ii) a data transfer CLI.

Data Transfer Lib

The data transfer library provides an API to transfer data from supported data providers to consumers, through public methods for:

- Bidirectional data transfer from HPC and CKAN,
- Bidirectional data transfer from HPC and HDFS,
- Bidirectional data transfer from HDFS and CKAN,
- Bidirectional data transfer from CKAN and any computing utility (e.g. Laptop, workstation).

In any of these methods, API callers can specify the i) data source details, including the data access account, and ii) the data destination (i.e. target), together with the data access account as well. The data to transfer can be specified by folders and wildcards (for fine-grained selection). Transferring recursive directories is also supported.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	28 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

CKAN access is granted by the CKAN API Key. HDFS access is granted by the Kerberos principal account. HPC access is granted by SSH accounts, private keys, certificates and optional 2FA tokens.

Transfer from/to all EuroHPC centres is supported. For those requiring VPN access, the NIFI server has been white-listed.

This library is implemented in Python 3, with Poetry [40] project and dependency management. The library is pre-configured for HiDALGO2 NIFI and Keycloak IDM. Specific user's configuration is managed in user's local home: `~/.dtcli/dtcli.cfg`. This configuration manages the:

- User account in the HiDALGO2 Keycloak,
- User account (using SSH keys) for the HiDALGO2 NIFI server: it is required for transferring HPC keys to NIFI². This approach will be replaced, in future work, by borrowing user's keys from the HiDALGO2 Vault support for secrets.

The data transfer lib code base is available at HiDALGO2 Gitlab [41]. Consult more details of its configuration and usage at its *README.md*.

As aforementioned, the data transfer library supports the different HPC access security-enabled mechanisms, including SSH, 2FA and VPN. Support for SSH accounts, keys and certificates is provided by NIFI processors. Support for VPN has been enabled in NIFI by using customised script-based *ExecuteStreamCommand* processors that capture the HPC prompt for 2FA token. For these reason, customised NIFI pipelines to transfer data from/to HPC with 2FA enabled have been implemented. In the library, a 2FA callback is required to prompt for the 2FA token upon the connection to the HPC.

Different optimizations have been incorporated, along this development period, to the data transfer library, both at NIFI level and code-base level, to speed up the transfer rate and to manage fault-tolerance.

At NIFI level, three main optimizations have been applied or explored: i) tweaking NIFI configuration to maximize the utilization of server resources, in terms of computing, memory and network bandwidth, ii) using the NIFI capability for parallel flowfile stream processing and iii) designing data transfer pipelines with forked parallel execution lines. This last optimization does not provide significant advantage over the built-in NIFI parallel flowfile stream processing and suffer of rigid pipeline architecture, as adding additional forked parallel execution lines required manual implementation and deployment. For this reason, the main adopted optimization was to rely on the NIFI capacity to process parallel transfer with customizable processor tasks, whose number can be programmatically set. Complementing these optimizations, the NIFI data

² HPC SSH keys are only kept in NIFI server during the data transfer and removed upon termination or failure rollback.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	29 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

transfer pipelines manage fault-tolerance, by adopting NIFI retries in failure connections.

At code base level, the initial approach consisted on executing the NIFI pipeline one processor after another, with fine-grain control over the pipeline execution. This introduced some extra latency while waiting for each processor to exhausts its incoming flowfiles. The following optimization in the data transfer lib implemented support for running the entire flowfile at once, so that the flowfiles are streamed through the pipeline processors with no latency. See section 0 for an evaluation of the Data Transfer framework performance.

To use the library, install it with `pip install hid_datatransfer_lib` or add its dependency to your Poetry `pyproject.toml`.

The published versions of the data transfer lib are available at pypi.org [42].

Documentation of the data transfer lib is available at the Hidalgo2 WIKI [43].

Data Transfer CLI

The Data Transfer CLI provides a shell client to the Data Transfer Library, intended to be used by final users as a command line tool. It offers the same Data Transfer Lib features, wrapped with a shell script interface.

Its default configuration is taken from the Data Transfer Lib. It can be overridden, and complemented with the customized user's specific settings, by editing the user's home `~/dtcli/dtcli.org`.

To reduce the number of parameters to pass through the CLI command, data providers/consumers can be specified in `~/dtcli/server_config` YAML file, adopting an approach similar to SSH config to declare SSH hosts. For instance, within this configuration file, you can declare your HPC centres, by setting the host, your username and SSH key path, so that you don't need to pass this information for each CLI command, as missed parameters will be read from this configuration file.

The Data Transfer CLI code base is available at Hidalgo2 Gitlab [44]. Consult more details of its configuration and usage at its *README.md*.

The published versions of the data transfer lib are available at pypi.org [45].

Documentation of the data transfer lib is available at the Hidalgo2 WIKI [46].

To install the CLI tool, use `pip install data_transfer_cli`.

2.4.3.4 Data Transfer from Cloud

NIFI's availability and capabilities enable the implementation of solutions to obtain meteorological data from several data providers and then store them in CKAN or HDFS and then make accessing them from any available HPC. In turn, these data can be

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	30 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

used as input data for any simulations or calculations within the HiDALGO2 pilot's workflows.

The general pipeline of any of these processes takes advantage of the framework detailed in the previous section and is adapted to the specificities of each data provider. In general terms, a specific connection to the Cloud provider is developed, the data is obtained and temporarily stored as a flowfile by NIFI and then sent to be stored with its corresponding metadata in CKAN or HDFS.

The services supported or expected to be supported are the following:

- MeteoFrance - ARPEGE model [47]
 - o To access the ARPEGE model it is needed to have an APIKEY provided by MeteoFrance and that gives access to their online API. Then, the user needs to provide the request parameters (subsets, datasets, coverage ids, etc.) as needed in MeteoFrance's implementation of the WCS standard [48]. Currently, the method `meteofrance2ckan`, available in the Data Transfer Library is able to request the data for one parameter and one datetime to a single file and store it in CKAN. Further improvements to handle the download of multiple files at the same time are being planned.
 - o Following the same schema described above it is currently being developed `meteofrance2hdfs` which follows the same logic already described but storing the data in HDFS.
 - o Additionally, these implementations will be later configured in the Data Transfer CLI.
- ECMWF model [49] – The ECMWF maintains packages that give access to their data and models. There are two main options available for our purposes, one for registered users and another one for ECMWF open data.
 - o An attempt was made with the first package but the download times were so long that it was deemed unusable and the resulting NIFI pipelines very difficult to test. The pipeline designed executed a python script that invoked the ECMWF package and downloaded the data according to the input arguments provided, this data was afterwards transformed into a flowfile and uploaded to CKAN.
 - o This same pipeline will be adapted to work with the ECMWF open data service and packages as `ecmwf2ckan` and later `ecmwf2hdfs`.
 - o Additionally, these implementations will be later configured in the Data Transfer CLI.
- It is also under consideration to test a third model, probably the Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD)'s ICON model [50].

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	31 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

2.4.3.5 KUB dataset and Multi-Backend Data Management

This section describes the KUB contribution to HiDALGO2 D4.2 through *kub-dataset*. The objective is to provide reproducible dataset packaging and transfer across multiple data management platforms (CKAN, HDFS, S3-compatible storage), while preserving a single user workflow.

kub-dataset design and dataset layout

kub-dataset (see Figure 5) manages location datasets as versioned assets (*vX.Y.Z*) with a current pointer for operational selection. This supports patch/minor/major update policies while keeping reproducible historical snapshots available. Local path resolution is centralized in the path manager layer so tooling can transparently consume flat or versioned datasets.

Operationally, the CLI delegates storage operations to a backend factory and a common backend protocol (push, pull, list_locations, list_versions, component-level operations). This design isolates platform-specific logic and allows the same command set to target different storage systems.

Backend focus: NIFI facade + native connectors

For HiDALGO2 integration, the HiDALGO2 backend acts as a NIFI-based transfer facade through *hid_data_transfer_lib* (see section 2.4.3.3):

- CKAN-oriented pipelines: local2ckan, ckan2local.
- HDFS-oriented pipelines: local2hdfs, hdfs2local (method-name compatibility handling included).
- Optional proxy fallback to native CKAN/HDFS connectors when a NIFI transfer call fails.

In parallel, native connectors are available and can be used directly:

- **CKAN backend:** package/resource lifecycle through CKAN API.
- **HDFS backend:** hierarchical archive storage and retrieval.
- **S3 backend:** S3-compatible object storage (AWS-compatible and MinIO-target model), including web-identity flow for temporary credentials.

This provides resilience: NIFI for orchestrated transfer workflows, native backends for continuity and diagnostics.

Login and tenant management

Authentication uses Keycloak/OIDC providers with:

- interactive PKCE browser login,
- non-interactive login for automation,

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	32 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

- token/context propagation to backends.

The same auth context carries organization identity, enabling tenant-aware routing (e.g., CKAN organization selection, S3 bucket naming convention, HDFS path partitioning by organization).

Metrics and future capabilities

The current architecture already exposes the basis for operational observability. Recommended future metrics:

- transfer throughput/latency by backend and archive type;
- NIFI success rate, fallback rate, and retry/recovery time;
- integrity and quality metrics (checksum pass rate, manifest/schema validation status);
- version governance indicators (patch cadence, age of current, rollback frequency);
- access/security telemetry (login success/failure, token refresh issues, per-organization volume).

A practical next step is standardized event export per transfer operation (JSON/Prometheus-compatible), to unify monitoring across CKAN, HDFS, S3, and NIFI execution paths.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	33 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Architecture sketch

Figure 5 architecture of kub-dataset

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	34 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

2.5 DMS Evaluation

The CKAN-powered data transfer platform was evaluated by conducting performance testing using CKAN2HPC-Client. The data was transferred between PSNC and Czestochowa University of Technology. For testing we used files of 1, 2, 5 and 10 GB.

Figure 6 Data upload using CKAN2HPC-Client

Compared to the CKAN API, uploading files via SFTP is faster (see Figure 6). Moreover, the performance gap increases with file size, with SFTP showing a clear advantage for larger files. In contrast, download times are comparable between the two approaches (see Figure 7).

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	35 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 7 Data download using CKAN2HPC-Client

The NIFI-powered data transfer platform, through the library or the CLI has been tested qualitatively and quantitatively against the EuroHPC centres.

Qualitatively, we tested both the library and the CLI can be used to transfer dataset from CKAN and HDFS to any EuroHPC centres, testing the access with SSH accounts, keys and certificates (e.g. Leonardo HPC), as well as 2FA (e.g. Vega or Deucalion HPCs) and VPN (Discoverer HPC).

Quantitative, we have benchmarked the throughput of the data transfer library (and CLI) by sending the same datasets across CKN, HDFS and LUMI HPC, and how this throughput, measure as the transfer rate (i.e., bytes transferred per second) have been improved along the development of performance improvements in the data transfer framework.

As a reminder, the following main optimizations have been implemented along the last development period:

- Optimization 1: NIFI parallel data transfer through multiple processor tasks and optimal NIFI resources configuration,
- Optimization 2: Parallel data transfer in CKAN custom processors,

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	36 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

- Optimization 3: NIFI pipeline execution in streaming mode, versus pipeline execution per processor until completion.

In the following, we discuss the throughput improvement comparing the results after optimizations 1, and 2 - 3.

After the optimization 1, the figures in Annex III (Figure 14, Figure 15 y Figure 16) show the throughput (as transferred bytes per second) for bidirectional data transfer of 1Gb of data among CKAN, HDFS and LUMI HPC versus the number of NIFI concurrent tasks involved in the transfer. Data consists of multiple data folders in HPC and HDFS, and few zipped datasets in CKAN. For each number of concurrent tasks, 10 full data transfers are performed, collecting transfer times, and computing the transfer rates and the standard deviation.

To understand the results, let's mention that CKAN, NIFI and HDFS services are deployed in VM nodes within the same PSNC Virtual Cloud, therefore, in the same local network. As shown in the figures, for most of cases, the throughput quickly increases from `#concurrent_tasks = 1` (i.e., sequential transfer) to saturate around `#_concurrent_tasks = 10`. Around this number for the resources of the NIFI node saturate, mostly in terms of network bandwidth. Beyond this point, no higher data transfer throughput is achieved by increasing the number of concurrent tasks. An exception to this behaviour is the transfer from HDFS to CKAN, as our pipelines, when transferring to CKAN, packages all the source files into a single zip file, as it makes no sense to transfer individual folder files to CKAN. For this reason, any advantage in getting files from HDFS in parallel are diluted when zipping the single file that is transferred to CKAN.

The speed up on throughput with the concurrency transfer ranges from no significant improvement in HDFS to CKAN transfer, 3X in CKAN to HDFS transfer, 6X in the HPC to CKAN transfer, 7X in HDFS to HPC transfer, 8X in CKAN to HPC transfer, and 13X in HPC to HDFS. Transfer from/to HPC gets the highest speed up due to the high latency to transfer data to remote HPCs, while transferring between HDFS and CKAN, in the same local network, gets lower speed up.

As a summary, parallel data transfer obtains gains between 3x and 13X with the number of concurrent tasks, before saturating the network transfer capabilities of the NIFI server.

Figure 17, Figure 18 and Figure 19 in Annex III show the throughput for bidirectional data transfer rate among CKAN, HDFS and LUMI HPC versus the number of NIFI concurrent tasks involved in the transfer, after applying the optimizations 2 and 3. Excepting when transferring data from CKAN to HPC, these optimizations cause a

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	37 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

significant boost in data transfer rate. The transfer rate from HPC to CKAN increases from a maximum of 12 Mb/s up to 16 Mb/s. Similarly, the transfer rate from CKAN to HDFS increases from a maximum of 60 Mb/s up to 90 Mb/s. In the case of HDFS to CKAN the top transfer rate increases from 35 Mb/s up to 55 Mb/s. Finally, the rate for transfer from HPC to HDFS slightly grows from 13 Mb/s up to 19 Mb/s, while another way around slightly scales from 38 Mb/s up to 43 Mb/s.

Improvements while transferring from CKAN are justified by the optimized parallel download of CKAN datasets, but the boost of performance for the case of HPC to CKAN cannot be explained as a single zip dataset is transferred to CKAN. As the network conditions for data transfer from HPC to CKAN cannot be fixed in the experiment, they could be sources of uncertainty. The boost on performance caused by the third optimization is expected to be modest for large transferred data, but not neglectable. When transferring to CKAN, before the compressed file is created, we need the pipeline to wait for all source data to arrive, so a synchronization point is established, reducing the speed up boosted by pipeline’s streaming flow processing. We can also observe uploading to HPC is faster than downloading from it.

To conclude this analysis, a summary of the data transfer benchmarks is presented in Table 3 , showing how the NIFI-powered data transfer can scale up from sequential transfer by adopting parallel execution.

Table 3 Data Transfer Benchmarks

Transfer direction	Maximum reported throughput	Maximum speed-up
HDFS → CKAN	up to 60 Mb/s	1.5×
CKAN → HDFS	up to 90 Mb/s	9×
HPC → CKAN	up to 16 Mb/s	8×
CKAN → HPC	up to 45 Mb/s	5×
HDFS → HPC	up to 40 Mb/s	5.5×
HPC → HDFS	up to 13 Mb/s	13×

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	38 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

3 Coupling Technologies

This section introduces the technological developments conducted and the technologies adopted for the realization of the different pilots' coupling scenarios described WP5 deliverables [3] [8]. The following subsections provides these details organized by coupling scenarios.

3.1 UAP and UBM coupling

This section reports the technical implementation activities carried out, and planned, for the realization of the coupling between the Urban Air Project (UAP) and the Urban Building Model (UBM), implemented on the UNISTRA side through KUB and its Feel++-based infrastructure. The objective of this coupling is to enable the exchange of interface quantities between the urban airflow simulation and the building-scale thermal simulation, so that the local atmospheric state computed by UAP can influence the thermal response of buildings, while the thermal state of buildings can be fed back to the urban CFD computation.

The integration work has been structured around two complementary technical routes, reflecting the two UAP execution branches discussed during the joint design meeting (see Figure 8). The first route targets the OpenFOAM-based UAP workflow and relies on preCICE [51] as the coupling framework. This choice was retained because OpenFOAM already provides mature support for preCICE, which reduces integration effort and allows the KUB side to focus on implementing a dedicated Feel++/KUB coupling adapter. The second route targets the RedSIM workflow and relies on a lightweight MPI interoperability layer based on `MPI_Open_port`, `MPI_Comm_accept` and `MPI_Comm_connect`. This second route avoids introducing a heavier coupling dependency when preCICE integration is not available or not desired. Earlier file-based exchange mechanisms were discussed, but they were considered insufficient for the main two-way coupling loop because they do not address efficiently the synchronization requirements of tightly coupled large-scale simulations.

From the code interoperability viewpoint, the first technical activity consists in defining a shared and versioned coupling contract. This contract specifies the structure of the interface mesh to be exchanged by the two codes, including vertex coordinates, optional triangle connectivity, patch or region labels, and stable vertex identifiers. These elements are required to guarantee consistent interpretation of the coupling

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	39 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

surface by both participants and to support reproducible mappings between non-matching meshes. In addition, the coupling contract defines the first set of exchanged fields and their associated units, conventions and directions. On the KUB-to-UAP side, the initial boundary quantities are the surface temperature and, in a later stage, sensible or latent heat fluxes. On the UAP-to-KUB side, the exchanged quantities are the near-wall air temperature, pressure, wind velocity or an equivalent convective exchange coefficient. This work corresponds to a concrete schema adaptation effort, since the internal field representations of Feel++/KUB and the UAP solvers must be mapped onto a shared interface description.

A second important implementation activity concerns the **handling of non-matching interface discretizations**. Since the interface meshes used by UAP and UBM are not expected to coincide, an interpolation and transfer layer is required. The baseline mapping strategy retained during the design discussion is barycentric interpolation on triangulated surfaces, with nearest-vertex or nearest-element transfer kept as a fallback option. The exchanged quantities are planned to be represented primarily at interface vertices rather than per face, since this yields smoother field transfers, lighter payloads and a more natural interpolation workflow. Corresponding sign conventions for normals and fluxes are also part of the interoperability specification and must be implemented consistently in both coupling routes.

For the **implementation of the OpenFOAM-based route**, the main code development is the implementation of a KUB preCICE participant. On the KUB side, this requires a thin adapter layer around the existing Feel++ field structures and coupling boundary representation. The adapter is responsible for registering the coupling mesh in preCICE, exporting the KUB-computed interface fields at the coupling times, importing the corresponding UAP fields, and applying them back to the UBM boundary conditions. The objective is to keep this first implementation minimal and focused on correctness, leaving performance-oriented refinements for a later phase. A dedicated toy demonstrator is planned to validate mesh registration, field round-trip consistency, interpolation correctness and coupling stability over a limited number of synchronized steps before moving to realistic urban geometries.

For the **implementation of the RedSIM-based route**, the main technical implementation is the development of a lightweight MPI interprocess communication library and protocol. A shared header will define the coupling API, message types and data layout for connection establishment, one-time geometry transfer and per-step field exchange. The first proof of concept will rely on blocking communication patterns, which are acceptable for this stage because timestep mismatch between the two

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	40 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

solvers is explicitly expected. In practice, one participant may reach the coupling point earlier and must wait for the other, and this synchronization behaviour has to be managed explicitly in the communication protocol. The MPI route therefore directly addresses the development of an interprocess communication library for UAP–UBM interoperability.

Challenges. The coupling design discussions also highlighted that the geometry exchange problem is not limited to transferring a watertight surface. This is particularly important for RedSIM, whose meshing pipeline requires contextual information such as refinement regions, near-ground resolution, street-canyon treatment and semantic distinctions between buildings, streets, vegetation or open areas. As a result, the development strategy does not assume immediate full automation of the RedSIM branch. Instead, the integration starts with two or three demonstrator cases for which the computational mesh can be prepared manually or with assisted procedures. These demonstrators will provide a controlled environment to validate the end-to-end data flow, the MPI communication layer and the physical plausibility of the exchanged fields before a more automated workflow is attempted.

Regarding **data exchange and workflow support**, the main coupling loop is intended to occur through direct runtime communication, either with preCICE or with MPI. However, HiDALGO2 data management components remain relevant for the preparation and traceability of the coupling scenario. CKAN, HDFS and the NIFI-based data transfer services can be used to store and transfer demonstrator datasets, geometry definitions, configuration files, logs and output fields produced by the coupled runs. In addition, workflow technologies such as MathSO and QCG are relevant for orchestrating the execution of the coupled jobs on HPC environments, especially for demonstrator deployment, dependency management and post-processing chains. In this sense, the UAP–UBM work combines direct interprocess exchange for the coupled runtime with DMS-based exchange for preparation, reproducibility and result management.

Another implementation aspect discussed concerns **packaging and access constraints**. Since KUB is not yet distributed as fully open source, the practical integration mode foreseen for collaboration is based on APIs, containers and test cases rather than unrestricted source sharing. This affects the deployment pipeline and requires the coupling demonstrators to be reproducible through packaged artefacts, documented run procedures and agreed interface specifications. This packaging work is therefore part of the technical integration effort.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies					Page:	41 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status:	Final

Figure 8 UAP-UBM coupling workflow

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	42 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

At the **current stage**, the main remaining tasks are to finalize the shared coupling contract, freeze the first minimum viable field set, implement the KUB preCICE adapter, implement the MPI open-port proof of concept for RedSIM, and validate both routes on toy cases before progressing to real urban demonstrators.

After these demonstrators, a further design decision will be taken on the long-term ownership of the canonical coupling surface, namely whether it should be primarily generated by KUB or by the RedSIM meshing chain. This staged implementation strategy reduces technical risk while keeping the work aligned with the overall HiDALGO2 data management, workflow orchestration and interoperability framework.

3.2 WFs and UAP coupling

Through this coupling, we aim to gain a better understanding of the threat that the various pollutants released during a fire may pose to the population in nearby urban areas.

To achieve this, we make use of WRF-SFIRE’s ability to utilise tracers. Tracer variables are three-dimensional concentration fields within the atmospheric grid that allow various pollutants present in smoke to be modelled as passive particles transported by the wind field. By coupling WRF-Chem with WRF-SFIRE, it is possible to use tracers for chemical species, which, in addition to being dispersed by the wind, undergo chemical reactions [52]. Although WRF-Chem is included in the WRF repository, simulations carried out with this model consume far more resources than those using tracers alone, which is why the latter approach has been discarded.

To account for the dispersion of pollutants considered most significant in terms of their potential impact on human health, emission factors associated with each type of fuel have been used. The emission factors used are based on studies carried out by the University of Aveiro, in Portugal. The selection of tracers in WRF is controlled by the name list variable *tracer_opt*; setting this to 2 enables the generation of up to 8 passive tracers named tr17_1 to tr17_8. Specifically, the emission factors depicted in Table 4 have been used.

To verify the functionality and suitability of the exchange file formats, several simulations were carried out in the Győr area at a resolution of 200 m; as a result, work has begun on coordinating the data flow to facilitate its operational implementation. It is important to note that no interprocess communication is envisaged.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	43 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Table 4 Emission factors

Pollutant	FT 01	FT 02	FT 03	FT 04	FT 05	FT 06	FT 07	FT 08	FT 09	FT 10	FT 11	FT 12	FT 13	FT 14
PM10	7.4	7.4	7.4	5.05	5.05	5.05	5.05	13.8	8.93	8.93	13.8	33.0	13.8	0
PM2.5	7.4	7.4	7.4	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	13.8	7.25	7.25	13.8	30.5	13.8	0
CO	57.3	57.3	57.3	95.5	95.5	95.5	95.5	69.9	150	150	69.9	129	69.9	0
CO2	1665	1665	1665	1605	1605	1605	1605	1684	1517	1517	1684	1506	1684	0
SO2	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	1.25	0.69	0.69	1.25	0.51	1.25	0
CH4	2.06	2.06	2.06	1.94	1.94	1.94	1.94	2.98	1.88	1.88	2.98	2.44	2.98	0
NO	3.73	3.73	3.73	2.43	2.43	2.43	2.43	1.64	2.17	2.17	1.64	1.62	1.64	0
NO2	4.8	4.8	4.8	0.82	0.82	0.82	0.82	1.48	1.85	1.85	1.48	0.95	1.48	0

The data flow designed is presented in the Figure 9.

WRF-SFIRE parametrization

The simulation was configured using three nested domains with horizontal resolutions of 3 km, 1 km, and 200 m, respectively. In order to analyse the generation and evolution of smoke plumes, two ignition points were defined sufficiently far apart from each other. The same microphysics, radiation, and land surface schemes were applied across all domains, specifically the WRF *Single-Moment 5-class* scheme (WSM5; mp_physics = 4), the RRTMG schemes for longwave and shortwave radiation (ra_lw_physics = 4 and ra_sw_physics = 4), and the Noah-MP land surface model (sf_surface_physics = 4). Regarding the planetary boundary layer parameterization, the Yonsei University (YSU; bl_pbl_physics = 1) scheme was used in the first two domains, whereas in the third

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	44 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

domain, due to its location within the so-called “gray zone,” the Shin–Hong scheme (bl_pbl_physics = 11) was employed.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	45 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 9 Data flow for the UAP-WFs coupling

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	46 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Tasks to be carried out to complete the integration:

- automating the coupling workflow:
 - data collection with NIFI-powered DMS Data Transfer (see section 2.4.3.1),
 - storing data in CKAN (see section 2.4.1),
 - running the WRF-Sfire model using data from CKAN,
 - transferring results to CKAN if it is needed,
 - running the UAP model using data from the HPC machine or CKAN.
- orchestrating WRF-Sfire (MathSO) [7],
- check that the data is useful to UAP and that the format is appropriate
- check the accuracy of the concentrations

In terms of the data transference needed to achieve the automation described, the NIFI Data Transfer API introduced on 2.2.2 will be used. This API can handle the download and storage of the input data required to run the simulations, in this particular case, the ECMWF’s open data will be readily retrieved and stored in CKAN using the NIFI Data Transfer Lib API designed to do so. Afterwards, once the simulations have been completed the API can be used to transfer back the results from the HPC to CKAN for storage and later analysis.

3.3 WFs and MTW coupling

Problem Statement

High-resolution wildfire simulations produce fire behaviour outputs, such as fire line intensity, rate of spread, and fuel consumption for each computational cell. However, they do not directly characterise the post-fire ash layer deposited on the ground. This ash layer is the primary source of fine sediment mobilised by the first post-fire rainfall events, generating erosion pulses and contamination loads that reach watercourses within hours. Quantifying the particle population per unit area (size distribution, number density, bulk density, and initial temperature) is therefore a critical link between wildfire modelling, water turbidity and hydro-sedimentological impact assessment.

Within HIDALGO2, the Wildfire (WF) pilot study will deliver a particle population dataset to the CFD sediment transport simulations (waLBerla) in the MWT pilot. The specific commitment is that, given BEHAVE [53] fire behaviour parameters for a 1 m² cell, provide the output vector (D_{inf,i} • D_{sup,i} • D_{rep,i} • m_i • ρ_{p,i} • N_i • T_{p,i}) ready for direct injection into the particle transport solver.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	47 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 10 Work-flow orchestration for the WF-MTW coupling

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	48 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

The data transfer requirements for this coupling follow the same considerations as those established for the UAP-WF coupling.

Strategy and Modelling Approach

The workflow adopts an empirical parametrisation strategy rather than a first-principles thermal model (see Figure 10). This choice is justified by two factors: (i) [54] explicitly note that attempts to relate fire line intensity directly to soil temperature have not been successful, as soil heating depends more on fuel moisture and flame residence time than on IB alone; and (ii) the uncertainty budget of a physically-derived model would be comparable to — or larger than — that of a well-constrained empirical look-up table. The approach is therefore presented as an order-of-magnitude estimate, not a physical prediction.

The coupling chain consists of five steps:

1. BEHAVE inputs: Fire line intensity (IB) [kW/m], reaction intensity IR [kW/m²], flame residence time τ [s], mass of fuel consumed M_c [kg/m²], time to rainfall t_{rain} [h], ambient temperature T_{amb} [°C].
2. Regime classification: IB classifies the combustion event into five regimes: Low (<100 kW/m), Moderate (100–500), High intensity (500–2000), Crown fire (>2000), and Smouldering duff (flagged separately, IB-independent).
3. Ash mass: M_{ash} [kg/m²] = $M_c \times f_{ash}$. The empirical ash conversion fraction f_{ash} ranges from 0.05–0.06 (crown fire) to 0.12–0.15 (low intensity / smouldering), derived from [55]. (2014) and [55].
4. Rosin-Rammler PSD: $F(D) = 1 - \exp[-(D/\bar{D})^n]$. Parameters D_{50} , n , D_{min} , D_{max} are assigned per regime ([55], Table 5). $\bar{D} = D_{50} / (\ln 2)^{(1/n)}$. Shape parameter $n \in [1.5, 2.0]$.
5. Particle population: Per class i : mass fraction from $F(D)$; D_{rep} as geometric mean of class bounds; variable density $\rho_p(D)$ from exponential char-to-mineral model; particle temperature T_p from Newton cooling of the ash layer.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	49 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Empirical Parameter Tables

All values derived from published field and laboratory measurements as indicated in the references (see Table 5 and Table 6).

Table 5. Empirical parameters (I)

Regime	IB [kW/m]	T_comb [°C]	T_soil [°C]	Ash type	D ₅₀ [µm]	f_ash
Low intensity	< 100	~450	100–200	Black/dark grey — organic char	150–300	0.12–0.15
Moderate	100–500	~600	200–300	Grey mixed — organic + mineral	50–150	0.08–0.12
High intensity	500–2000	~850	300–400	White mineral — carbonates + oxides	18–56	0.05–0.08
Crown fire	> 2000	~1200	100–200*	White mineral fine — short residence	18–40	0.05–0.06
Smoldering duff	duff-driven	~550	450–500	White mineral very fine — long duration	14–30	0.10–0.15

* Crown fire: lower T_{soil} because flame is elevated; short ground residence time. Sources: [55] Table 5; [54] Fig. 5;[57].

Table 6 Empirical parameters (II)

Regime	D ₅₀ [µm]	n	\bar{D} [µm]	D_min [µm]	D_max [µm]	ρ_{min} / ρ_{max} [kg/m ³] · D _ρ [µm]
Low intensity	200	1.5	241	50	1500	1200 / 1500 · D _ρ = 300
Moderate	100	2.0	113	20	800	1300 / 2000 · D _ρ = 150
High intensity	40	2.0	45	10	300	1800 / 2600 · D _ρ = 80
Crown fire	30	2.0	34	10	200	1700 / 2400 · D _ρ = 90
Smoldering	25	1.8	29	5	200	1800 / 2900 · D _ρ = 50

$\bar{D} = D_{50} / (\ln 2)^{(1/n)}$. Sources: [55] Tables 3–5; [57].

Implementation and Worked Example

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	50 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

The workflow is implemented as a Python post-processor (**behave_ash_particles.py**) requiring only numpy and pandas. For each BEHAVE scenario entered via console, it writes a CSV with one row per diameter class containing all seven output fields. Table 7 shows the verified result for a moderate-regime case.

Table 7 Verified result for a moderate-regime case

i	D_inf [μm]	D_sup [μm]	D_rep [μm]	m_i [g/m ²]	ρ_p [kg/m ³]	N_i [part/m ²]	T_p [°C]	Notes
1	20	98	44.3	36.70	1821	4.44 × 10 ⁸	57.9	95% of total mass
2	98	176	131.3	31.77	1592	1.68 × 10 ⁷	57.9	
3	176	254	211.4	8.43	1471	1.16 × 10 ⁶	57.9	
4	254	332	290.4	0.88	1401	4.87 × 10 ⁴	57.9	
5	332	410	368.9	0.04	1360	1.06 × 10 ³	57.9	< 0.01% mass

IB = 250 kW/m, M_consumed = 0.8 kg/m², t_rain = 6 h, T_amb = 20°C → M_ash = 0.080 kg/m², N_total = 4.62 × 10⁸ part/m². First 5 of 10 classes shown.

Results and Validation

The tool has been tested across all five fire regimes. Key observations:

- Mass conservation: Sum of class masses $\sum m_i$ recovers M_{ash} to numerical precision in all cases.
- Particle count order of magnitude: For a moderate-regime cell with $M_{ash} = 0.08 \text{ kg/m}^2$, $N_{total} \approx 4.6 \times 10^8 \text{ part/m}^2$, consistent with [55] estimates for similar fuel loads.
- Fine-class mass dominance: More than 90% of ash mass is contained in the two finest diameter classes in all regimes, reflecting the right-skewed Rosin-Rammler tail at the n values used.
- Density gradient: The $\rho_p(D)$ model yields 1200–2900 kg/m³ across regimes, bracketing values reported by [57] for char and mineral ash fractions.
- Particle temperature: For $t_{rain} = 6 \text{ h}$ and $\tau_{cool} = 3 \text{ h}$ (moderate), $T_p = 57.9^\circ\text{C}$ — above the ~60–80°C wettability threshold relevant for particle aggregation. For $t_{rain} > 24 \text{ h}$, $T_p \approx T_{amb}$ for all regimes.

Future Developments

The following extensions are planned or recommended for subsequent project phases:

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	51 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

- Fuel stratum disaggregation: Superimposing per-stratum PSDs (1h, 10h, 100h, herbaceous, live woody) would improve physical fidelity.
- Rosin-Rammler n calibration: Least-squares fitting of n to [55] Table 5 granulometric data would replace the current literature-range estimate.
- Bimodal PSD for smoldering: A two-component model (coarse char + sub-micron aerosols) would better represent smoldering duff ash.
- 1D heat transfer model (Level 2): A finite-difference solution of the 1D conduction equation in the litter layer — forced by IR and τ from BEHAVE — would provide a physically derived T_{soil} .
- Batch CSV input: Reading an ensemble of BEHAVE scenarios from a CSV file would support HPC-scale sensitivity studies across FBFM40 fuel models and meteorological conditions.
- Wettability module: Incorporating particle hydrophobicity as a function of T_p and combustion completeness would improve initial conditions for the sediment transport model.
- Coupling to WRF-Sfire: Replacing BEHAVE with WRF-Sfire fire behaviour outputs would enable direct coupling within the full HIDALGO2 HPC pilot workflow.

Visual simulation integration in Unreal Engine

The particle data is currently being used to develop a simulation showcase using the waLBerla software, enabling a fluid–particle coupled simulation scenario. At present, a visualization pipeline is being established to integrate these simulations into Unreal Engine. Once this pipeline is successfully implemented, it can be reused to visualize larger and more complex showcases that will be generated in the coming months. Achieving this milestone would represent a significant step forward in effectively coupling the two pilot projects. In addition, we plan to explore the possibility of developing multiple simulation showcases with varying parameters, allowing for a broader and more comprehensive demonstration of the coupling scenario.

3.4 RES and UBM coupling

The main purpose of the development of this system is the prediction of the energy production by defined energy sources. While this coupling has been envisioned and described in Deliverable D5.1 [2], here updates and details are depicted. Administrator

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	52 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

of each energy source who deliver energy to the power grid is obligate to declare predicted amount of energy. Additional fees from difference between real amount of energy produced and declared in advance cause this prediction very important procedure. More accurate prediction decreases fees. The main goal is increasing the energy prediction accuracy. RES.ENERGY tool based on AI training works better by providing more data correlated with the efficiency of the photovoltaic panel or wind turbines. Extension the data by results from KUB is proposed solution for increasing accuracy as developing the coupling between RES and KUB.

The coupling between RES and UBM is developed for weather forecasting used further in prediction of energy production by renewable energy sources as photovoltaic farms and wind turbines. The RES contains few tools in its pipeline: RES:WRF, RES:EULAG, and RES:ENERGY, where the information is passed to from one tool to the other. Each tool has specific goal to fulfil. RES:WRF provides the weather forecast in large scale, RES.EULAG refine the results to the very specific location. The RES:ENERGY is trained model by weather data collected from the simulations and on-site PV sensors, which is able to predict the energy amount production by specific energy source. All the data is exchanged by files. Additionally, the KUB is software designed for urban buildings insolation parameters simulations. The coupling between both software - RES and KUB - is realized by feeding the RES:ENERGY model additionally by KUB results. KUB provides additional information about the geometry of other building and obstacles shading. In that way, the energy prediction might be more accurate due to usage of the information on shading. In the whole process additional tools and software are used, e.g. Open Street Maps for detailed information on buildings and objects, or CKAN to store the output. The whole pipeline and technical details are presented below.

The development of the coupling is presented on two pilots. Kałolewo airport where photovoltaic farm is installed and hotel building in Konin town centre, where its roof is potential spot for photovoltaic panel installation (see Figure 11).

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	53 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 11. Coupling site locations

The work-flow of the whole RES-KUB coupling is presented in Figure 12. Purple and green colours represent each part of the coupling. Blue boxes are the data exchanged by files and yellow are additional tools or data servers.

Figure 12 Data workflow

Every simulation starts from defining the interested point by its GPS coordinates and area around defined by coordinates of four points representing corners of the rectangle. Additionally time period and time step are defined. After this step the necessary input files are generated. For longer time period or for sequential set of simulations (like one year with daily or 6 hours-time step) input files might be generated automatically just before its simulation. KUB by default using the Open Street Maps (OSM) to generate input files containing information about buildings. For compliance between KUB and RES:EULAG solvers and better usage of the results in

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	54 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

RES:ENERGY, additional tool was developed to prepare input files for RES:EULAG based on Open Street Maps as well. Right now both solvers use the same source of input data - it means OSM. The last development was focused to add other objects than defined in OSM as buildings. Currently also object defined as energy source are considered during creating input data from OSM. This upgrade allows to read the photovoltaic farm in Kałolewo (pilot mentioned above). It was necessary to provide the PV farm data, like direction (orientation), tilt angle of the panel, its max and min height to the OSM.

Another input data used in RES:EULAG comes from WRF solver or might be downloaded directly from CKAN (upon availability of the previously run simulations). RES:EULAG uses results containing: velocity (U10, V10), temperature T2, surface pressure and accumulated total cumulus precipitation. KUB - second solver also uses weather data as input data. They are directly downloaded from OpenMeteo (OM) server. They are: cloud cover, diffuse radiation, direct radiation, relative humidity 2m, surface pressure, temperature 2m, wind direction 10m, wind speed 10m. Both solvers might be run on the HPC machine at the same time. KUB solver is delivered as the singularity container. The work on contenerization of RES:EULAG is underway.

The next step is collecting all of the results in CKAN server. There is number of variable distributions stored from long time period simulations to provide necessary data for RES:ENERGY model. From RES:EULAG following results are considered: velocity (u, v, w), pressure, temperature, precipitation. From KUB - solar shading coef. Also directly from Open Meteo - cape, apparent temperature, precipitation, sunshine duration, weather code, wind gusts 10m, visibility and 'is day'

3.5 UBM and WRF coupling

The coupling between the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model and the Urban Building Model (UBM) aims to provide a high-fidelity distribution of meteorological variables driving the thermal response of urban structures. By transitioning from point-source weather data to three-dimensional spatiotemporal regional grids, the simulation accurately captures complex, localized atmospheric dynamics. For the primary Strasbourg test case, the WRF-Sfire simulation employs two nested domains with horizontal resolutions of 3 km and 1 km. Consistent physical parameterizations are applied across both domains to ensure numerical stability, including the WRF Single-Moment 5-class microphysics scheme, the New Goddard and Dudhia radiation schemes, the Noah-MP land surface model, and the Yonsei University planetary boundary layer scheme. The current architecture relies on a decoupled, asynchronous workflow (see Figure 13) where no direct inter-process

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	55 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

communication between WRF and UBM occurs during their respective execution times.

Workflow orchestration on EuroHPC environments relies on the MathSo and QCG platforms to manage dependencies, boundary data processing, and the complete WRF and WPS execution sequence. This environment is supported by the Spack package manager to ensure deployment portability. The execution is driven by the UNISTRA Ktirio Graphical User Interface, which processes user-defined parameters into structured JSON payloads to automatically generate WRF configuration scripts. Upstream data exchange, including static geographical data and dynamic global boundary conditions, is managed via CKAN, HDFS, and NIFI-powered DMS Data Transfer Lib workflows that interface with providers such as ECMWF and Meteo France.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	56 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 13 Work-flow orchestration for the UBM-WRF coupling

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	57 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Bridging the raw WRF spatialized outputs with UBM inputs requires a dedicated, automated C++ preparation routine. WRF natively generates a massive volume of data, outputting one discrete HDF5 file per timestep structured across longitude, latitude, and elevation dimensions. The C++ module ingests this sequence of files, filters the raw atmospheric data to extract surface-level variables (bypassing vertical atmospheric layers), computes necessary derived quantities on the fly, and aggregates the results into a single, unified 3D pivot HDF5 format encompassing latitude, longitude, and time. This consolidated HDF5 file serves as the definitive meteorological input for downstream processes and is managed via unique dataset identifiers within Data Management Systems using REST APIs. This design ensures data traceability and allows the reuse of validated spatial data across multiple urban scenarios without repeating computationally expensive atmospheric simulations.

To process these spatialized atmospheric grids natively, the UBM architecture underwent extensive object-oriented refactoring. The legacy monolithic parser was replaced by an abstract parent class implementing specialized child classes optimized for either zero-dimensional point-data or three-dimensional spatiotemporal grids. The system dynamically instantiates the appropriate model, ensuring the core simulator remains source-agnostic. Furthermore, the downstream C++ module reads the aggregated HDF5 files and executes real-time spatial interpolation utilizing Lagrange Q1 first-order finite element methods within the Feel++ framework. This yields precise meteorological values for specific building coordinates, which are subsequently injected directly into the Functional Mock-up Units in memory. This direct communication mechanism ensures strict synchronization between WRF timestamps and UBM simulation steps while mitigating disk-based input and output bottlenecks.

While the core computational components, spatial interpolation, and filtering routines are fully operational, current collaborative efforts focus on the end-to-end automation of the high-performance computing pipeline. Remaining integration objectives include finalizing the automated WRF deployment via MathSo and QCG, establishing the downstream UBM orchestration, and streamlining the asynchronous data lifecycle from data collection with the NIFI-powered Data Transfer to storage and model execution.

3.6 RES and WRF coupling

The core of the RES pilot are two weather forecasting applications: WRF running at meso scale, and EULAG running at local/city scale. The coupling between models is done one way, from WRF to EULAG, and information is exchanged via files, as described in deliverable D5.1. In the general single run, workflow begins with WRF execution, and once the job is finished, the data is passed to the EULAG model so that the execution of more detailed model can be started. The dynamic coupling,

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	58 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

making running WRF and EULAG in parallel exchanging data on the fly, is not considered. The reason for this is that the WRF is run on at least country level, and results are used by many other EULAG simulations, running at different regions/cities, and at different times within during the day. Moreover, such approach allows to use the data already being produced and store in CKAN. The coupling is additionally facilitated by using the QCG-Portal. Using this GUI, user can configure and run WRF as a part of the workflow, so that EULAG is automatically feed with the required input information. Or, data already available in CKAN can be used as initial parameters.

The last but not least step is to test the coupling with WRF provided by MTG project partner.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	59 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

4 Conclusions

This document has reported two main results of the HiDALGO2 project, namely, i) the functional specification, technical design and implementation, and performance evaluation of the HiDALGO2 Data Management System (DMS), and ii) the adoption and development of coupling technologies for the realization of the pilots' coupling scenarios.

The DMS provides foundational support for the provisioning of data required by exa-scale CFD simulations in HPC centres, from multiple data providers, including Cloud providers (e.g. ECMWF), HiDALGO2 storage (e.g. CKAN or HDFS) or other HPC centres. DMS offers scalable, flexible and highly efficient storage for large volumes of data, as well as for efficient data transfer among providers and HPC centres. Integrated within WFOs, the provisioning and deployment of pilot simulations can be easily automated. On data transfer, the DMS offers specialized transfer for CKAN, general purpose NIFI-powered transfer among several Cloud providers, DMS storage and HPC, and a KUB solution especially suited for pipeline integration. Moreover, data sharing and publication is reinforced with support for Zenodo's exportation.

Technical support for the realization of the HiDALGO2 coupling scenario has also been largely extended, as reported in this document. Not only the existing HiDALGO2 WFOs tooling for automatic coupling pipelines' deployment and execution, and the DMS tooling for data sharing and transfer has been largely adopted by the coupling scenarios. Other technical developments have been implemented, including i) adaptations in the pilots' codebases for sharing coupling contracts and interfaces (i.e., data schema and formats), ii) the integration of HiDALGO2 visualization techniques, iii) the development and adoption of light-weight MPI interoperability layers, or iv) the adoption of tightly-coupled frameworks, among others.

As future work beyond the scope of this document, the DMS development will focus on the integration of planned Cloud providers for the NIFI-powered data transfer as well as its further optimization with NIFI clusters. The future work on coupling scenarios will focus on the completion of the ongoing integration activities reported for each scenario in section 3.

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	60 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

References

1. Jesús Gorroñoigoitia et al, "D4.1 Data Management and Coupling Technologies," HiDALGO2 Report, 2023
2. Christophe Prud'homme et al, "D5.1 Achievements, Synergies and Coupled Simulations (M18)," HiDALGO2 Report, 2024.
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16715.40480>
3. Harald Koestler et al, "D5.4 Research Advancements for the Pilots (M23)," HiDALGO2 Report, 2024 <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23080.79368>
4. Flavio Cesar Cunha Galeazzo et al, "D3.7 Ensemble Scenarios for Global Challenges (M21)," HiDALGO2 Report, 2024
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28421.15841>
5. Flavio Cesar Cunha Galeazzo et al, "D4.9 Uncertainty Quantification (M26)," HiDALGO2 Report, 2025 <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20533.79845>
6. Konstantinos Nikas et al, "D3.2 Scalability, Optimization and Co-Design Activities (M22)," HiDALGO2 Report, 2024
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13842.36801>
7. Sameer Haroon et al, "D2.6 Infrastructure Provisioning, Workflow Orchestration and Component Integration (M35)," HiDALGO2 Report, 2025
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35110.38726>
8. Christophe Prud'homme et al, "D4.7 Visualisations for Global Challenges (M28)," HiDALGO2 Report, 2025
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23639.18086>
9. "CKAN DMS," [Online]. Available: <https://ckan.org/>
10. "NIFI Apache," [Online]. Available: <https://nifi.apache.org/>
11. Marcin Lawenda et al, "D2.1 Requirements Analysis and Scenario Definition," HiDALGO2 Report, 2023
12. Jesús Gorroñoigoitia et al, "D2.2 Requirements Analysis and Scenario Definition," HiDALGO2 Report, 2024
13. Marcin Lawenda et al, "D2.3 Requirements Analysis and Scenario Definition," HiDALGO2 Report, 2026

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	61 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

14. "CEPH," [Online]. Available: <https://ceph.io/en/>
15. "Keycloak IAM," [Online]. Available: <https://www.keycloak.org/>
16. "Kerberos Network Authentication Protocol," [Online]. Available: <https://web.mit.edu/kerberos/>
17. "Apache Hadoop," [Online]. Available: <https://hadoop.apache.org/>
18. "Apache Hadoop HDFS," [Online]. Available: <https://hadoop.apache.org/docs/stable/hadoop-project-dist/hadoop-hdfs/HdfsDesign.html>
19. "The European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU)," [Online]. Available: https://www.eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/index_en
20. "Jupyter Hub," [Online]. Available: <https://jupyter.org/hub>
21. "Apache Spark," [Online]. Available: <https://spark.apache.org/>
22. "Apache Hadoop YARN," [Online]. Available: <https://hadoop.apache.org/docs/current/hadoop-yarn/hadoop-yarn-site/YARN.html>
23. "Apache Ambari," [Online]. Available: <https://ambari.apache.org/>
24. "Docker," [Online]. Available: <https://www.docker.com/>
25. "Kubernetes," [Online]. Available: <https://kubernetes.io/>
26. "Helm, Kubernetes Package Manager," [Online]. Available: <https://helm.sh/>
27. "Apache Hive," [Online]. Available: <https://hive.apache.org/>
28. "Apache Atlas," [Online]. Available: <https://atlas.apache.org>
29. "Apache Hudi," [Online]. Available: <https://hudi.apache.org/>
30. "Apache Livy," [Online]. Available: <https://livy.apache.org/>
31. "Sparkmagic," [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/jupyter-incubator/sparkmagic>
32. "HUE," [Online]. Available: <https://gethue.com/>
33. "Zenodo," [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/>
34. "Zabbix," [Online]. Available: <https://www.zabbix.com/>

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	62 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

35. "Flask," [Online]. Available: <https://flask.palletsprojects.com/en/stable/>
36. "Waitress WSGI Server," [Online]. Available: <https://pypi.org/project/waitress/>
37. "RabbitMQ," [Online]. Available: <https://www.rabbitmq.com/>
38. "CKAN API," [Online]. Available: <https://docs.ckan.org/en/2.9/api/>
39. "HiDALGO2 GitLab CKAN custom processors," [Online]. Available: <https://git.hidalgo2.eu/hidalgo2-group/hid-data-management/-/tree/develop/data-transfer/nifi/customed-processors>
40. "Poetry Python packaging and dependency management," [Online]. Available: <https://python-poetry.org/>
41. "Data Transfer Lib source code," [Online]. Available: https://git.hidalgo2.eu/hidalgo2-group/hid-data-management/-/tree/develop/data-transfer/nifi/hid_data_transfer_lib
42. "Data Transfer Lib at Pypi.org," [Online]. Available: https://pypi.org/project/hid_data_transfer_lib/
43. D. T. L. W. Documentation. [Online]. Available: <https://wiki.hidalgo2.eu/h2/software/dtlib>
44. "Data Transfer CLI source code," [Online]. Available: <https://git.hidalgo2.eu/hidalgo2-group/hid-data-management/-/tree/develop/data-transfer/nifi/data-transfer-cli>
45. "Data Transfer CLI at Pypi.org," [Online]. Available: <https://pypi.org/project/data-transfer-cli/>
46. "Data Transfer CLI WIKI Documentation," [Online]. Available: <https://wiki.hidalgo2.eu/h2/software/dtcli>
47. "Meteofrance ARPEGE model," [Online]. Available: <https://portail-api.meteofrance.fr/web/en/api/ARPEGE>
48. "WCS Standard," [Online]. Available: <https://www.ogc.org/standards/wcs/>
49. "ECMWF model," [Online]. Available: <https://www.ecmwf.int/en/research/modelling-and-prediction>
50. "Deutscher Wetterdienst ICON model," [Online]. Available: https://www.dwd.de/EN/ourservices/nwp_forecast_data/nwp_forecast_data.html

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	63 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

51. "preCICE," [Online]. Available: <https://precice.org/>

52. "Smoke coupling with WRF-Chem," [Online]. Available: https://wiki.openwfm.org/wiki/Smoke_and_coupling_with_WRF-Chem

53. "Behave Fire Modeling System," [Online]. Available: <https://www.frames.gov/behave/home>

54. Hungerford, R.D., Harrington, M.G., Frandsen, W.H., Ryan, K.C., Niehoff, G.J., "Influence of fire on factors that affect site productivity.," *USDA Forest Service Gen. Tech. Rep. INT-280*

55. Bodí, M.B., Martin, D.A., Balfour, V.N., Santín, C., Doerr, S.H., Pereira, P., Cerdà, A., Mataix-Solera, J. Wildland, "fire ash: Production, composition and eco-hydro-geomorphic effects.," *Earth-Science Reviews*, vol. 130, p. 103–127. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2013.12.007>

56. Duran, C.M. et al, "Fuels, vegetation, and prescribed fire dynamics influence ash production and characteristics in a mixed-conifer forest.," *Fire Ecology*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42408-018-0015-7>

57. Gabet, E.J., Bookter, A, "Physical, chemical and hydrological properties of Ponderosa pine ash," *International Journal of Wildland Fire*, vol. 20(3), no. 443–452. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1071/WF09105>

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	64 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Annex I: CKAN-Zenodo exporter – configuration example

[app]

secret_key=[A RANDOM KEY]

log_file=[PATH TO LOG FILE]

[ckan]

server=https://ckan.example.com

apikey=[CKAN API KEY]

resources_path=/mnt/vol/ckan/default/resources

resources_usr_path=/mnt/vol/homes/{user}/ckan-pub

resources_usr_url=https://ckan.example.com:8443/~

[mysql]

host = localhost

user =

password =

database = zenodo_export

[sso]

keycloak_server_url =

realm_name =

client_id =

client_secret =

redirect_uri =

[rabbitmq]

host = localhost

queue = zenodo_upload

[zenodo]

api_url = <https://zenodo.org/api/deposit/depositions>

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	65 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Annex II: CKAN2HPC-Client – configuration example

[ckan]

url=https://ckan.example.com
organization=EXAMPLARY_ORGANIZATION
api_token=CKAN_API_TOKEN

[sftp]

server_address=ckan.example.com
server_web_port=8443
username=example_user
private_key=/home/user/.ssh/id_rsa

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	66 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Annex III: Performance benchmarking of Data Transfer Tool (Charts)

Figure 14 CKAN2HPC Data Transfer throughput (Mb/s) vs # concurrent transfer tasks after optimization 1

a) above, for CKAN to HPC transfer, b) below, for HPC 2 CKAN transfer

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	67 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 15 Data Transfer throughput (Mb/s) vs # concurrent transfer tasks after optimization 1

b) a) above, for CKAN to HDFS transfer, b) below, for HDFS 2 CKAN transfer

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	68 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 16 Data Transfer throughput (Mb/s) vs # concurrent transfer tasks after optimization 1

a) above, for HPC to HDFS transfer, b) below, for HDFS 2 HPC transfer

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	69 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 17 CKAN2HPC Data Transfer throughput (Mb/s) vs # concurrent transfer tasks after optimizations 2 and 3

a) above, for CKAN to HPC transfer, b) below, for HPC 2 CKAN transfer

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	70 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 18 CKAN2HDFS Data Transfer throughput (Mb/s) vs # concurrent transfer tasks after optimizations 2 and 3

a) above, for CKAN to HDFS transfer, b) below, for HDFS 2 CKAN transfer

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	71 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 19 HPC2HDFS Data Transfer throughput (Mb/s) vs # concurrent transfer tasks after optimizations 2 and 3

a) above, for HPC to HDFS transfer, b) below, for HDFS 2 HPC transfer

Document name:	D4.2 Data Management and Coupling Technologies				Page:	72 of 72
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final